

Exploring the Style of Khushwant Singh's Writing

By

Sonaji Baldevji Rajput

Research Scholar

Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University

Bhavnagar, 364001, India

&

(Research Supervisor)

Dr. Hetal J. Mehta

Principal

Swami Sahajanand College of Commerce & Management,

Affiliated to Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University.

Bhavnagar-364002, Gujarat, India

Abstract:

Style in linguistic work means the use of certain features to bring out certain expressions, feelings or thoughts so as to be impactful on readers' mind. Each and every thought should be expressed through meaningful words or by forming sentences. Khushwant Singh, best known for his switching style of writing as editor, journalist, novelist, storywriter, historian, columnist, and poet is one of the eminent literary personalities in the Indian Literary World. His supreme contribution to the Indian literary world is just praiseworthy. He has portrayed every emotion on the piece of paper with skillful convention of his pen and he has to his credit the remarkable novels like *I Shall Not Hear Nightingale*, *Train to Pakistan*, *The Company of Women*, *Delhi*. Great sense of humor, sharp sarcasm, clarity of ideas, great characterization, situation crafting aptitude are some of attributes summarizes the styles of Khushwant Singh's pen. This paper is an attempt to understand the styles or the attributes of writing by Khushwant Singh in various forms of masterpieces of his literary work. He was best known for his secularism, realism, humor, sarcasm and his love of poetry.

Key words: style, stylistic, linguistic, attributes, literary work

Style: An Introduction

Style can be defined as “Proper words in proper places” while analyzing the writing style of any literary professional. The word ‘style’ seems to be very simple and common word and even familiar to everyone. Analyzing one’s style creates a curiosity in itself and it has its own significance with some its own peculiarities and elegance specifically while analyzing one’s way of speaking or writing. Style gives a definite identity to the piece of work created and nurtured in the discipline of literary. While expressing thoughts, emotions, the manner in which those expressions are been served mean a lot to the eminence of the literary work.

Cambridge Dictionary defines Style as “a way of doing something, especially one that is typical of a person, group of people, place or period.”

Lexico powered by Oxford defines, “Style is a way of using language.” (Buffon)

Early 14c., stile was meant as the writing instrument, pen, and stylus, piece of written discourse even known as characteristic rhetorical mode of an author or a mode of expression. Originally Latin word “*stilus*” and from Old French “*stile/estile*” which meant an instrument for writing and a manner of writing.

Style means manner of writing, mode of expressing thought in language: the distinctive manner peculiar to an author: characteristic or peculiar mode of expression and execution. (Cambridge Dictionary)

According to The Routledge Dictionary of Literary Terms,” A style is a manner of expression, describable in linguistic terms, justifiable and valuable in respect of non-linguistic factors. The concept ‘manner of expression’ is controversial (see below), but the other two parts of the definition seem not to be: that it is a facet of language; and that it is given significance by personal or cultural, rather than verbal, qualities.”

As per Richard Ohmann, "A style is a way of writing-that is what the word means."

Georges Louis Leclerc Buffon quotes, “The style is the man himself.”

“Style is a writer’s individual mode of expression, way of putting his conceptions into words. It involves a long list of choices at paradigmatic and syntagmatic axes: choice of lexical items, use of tropes and figures of speech, phrasal and syntactic structures and the shape of paragraphs. These choices make the writer an individual as clearly discernible and differentiable as he is in the frequency and quality of his voice, in his behavioral idiosyncrasies and ways of walking and laughing. It is the whole of man, the whole of his self that speaks through his style.” (Ghulam)

Khushwant Singh and his style of writing:

When somebody wishes to explore somebody’s style, both linguistic and literary perception needs to be studied. Being stylistic means individual’s use of language which reflects his or her unique personality, thought process, thinking ability and many more. And that’s what the style of Khushwant Singh. His effortless writing has always been distinct and live. The supremacy of his transcends language though ordinarily understood has always created a stunning success crafting any theme, aesthetic concept, characters. Khushwant Singh was always been successful to present uniqueness to his pen so as to create history in the literary world.

Khushwant Singh was born to the Sikh family in the year 1915 in Hadali, Punjab and lived as a creative writer till his last breath. He was one of the best historian, novelist and the finest commentator. The whole of his life, he accompanied by his best companion, “his pen”. He created a history as played multidimensional roles with his sword like ink and honored as one of the distinguished men of letters. He has devoted to the world of literature as fearless intellectual. He was very eminent writer in English language having an international reputation. He served Indian Foreign Service, served as journalist at All India Radio, in Mass Communication. His eternal assessment skills have made him the most eligible writer to make the funniest comparison of the social and behavioral traits of people from India and West. He is believed as the most courageous and penetrative writer of his time. Being one of the most renowned personalities, he has authored number of great literary works like *Train to Pakistan* (1956), *I Shall Not Hear the Nightingale* (1959), *Delhi* (1989), *The Company of Women* (1999), and many more. He has been described as the humorous writer and incorrigible believer in human goodness with a devil may-care attitude and a courageous mind by the Chief Minister of Andhra Pradesh.

Train to Pakistan has tagged him as the partition writer. His style to provide vividness to the text and crafting the breathing incidents on the piece of paper has helped him to show his disenchantment with the world. His felt bitter experiences of autumn 1947 created a history of its own time in the year 1956 which made people live and experience the partition of India with one of his finest creations *Train to Pakistan*. *Train to Pakistan*, he has drawn a picture of partition experiences the reader the pain of life, war, life of slums, mental disorders, injustice. The use of earth idioms always added the salty flavor to his literary works. It was the first time Khushwant Singh has tried his pen.

Khushwant Singh's presence of mind always lent a hand to know what the readers want. It was an aptitude of his acute keenness towards every stream, penetration of thoughts and his exceptional intellect made him so realistic in his thought process. He has the collection of short stories to his name which unearths the hidden talent of creative writing. He has created his characters in imagination at such an extent that he would be in a position to move ahead with his stories. It is the literary style of Khushwant Singh that he used to put his all story characters in a specific situation and then used to do the psychoanalysis so as to understand the reason and rationale behind the actions and reactions as human action. His clarity of thoughts always helped him induced the behaviour of the reader and keep them caught along with his stories and stories characters.

It is been observed that he has been the most popular writer of his time even though highly attacked by many controversies. He was a gifted psychoanalyst could make out the pulses of his readers as to what they like and they dislike for being advantageous in catering the same of their expectations and choice. Because of his candid and unique style, he has remained the fondest of writer of his readers. He was one of the finest historians and social critic. It was a proud of every bookshelf to carry the graceful work by Khushwant Singh.

Literary and Linguistic Stylistics in Khushwant Singh's work:

Khushwant Singh with his linguistic perspective has made his style more and more standardized, vivid and practical. He has enjoyed full freedom to select and implement various linguistic features from the level of sounds, words, sentences, paragraphs and even a text as a whole to make his creativity more ornamental. His aptness in using phonological features made his

writing more expressive. The use of rhyming and alliterative words has created a comic effect. This reflects the proficiency of his English language. To illustrate few like “Papdams and Pakoras” from “*Not a Nice Man to Know*”, “Kupu Kupu Kalam” and “Lahore is just a half-hour hop away from Delhi” from, “*Many Moods and Many Faces*” gave the native touch to the incident.

Creating a total language effect is just a magic by Khushwant Singh. Use of rhyming words and his expertise using assonant sounds produced real time effects in his writing. He has used the Indian languages mostly Hindi and Punjabi to add on spices to his writing like Instead of putting it as the voice of four wheeler, “Poh Poh” from “*Women and Men in My Life*”, “Naam vaam to main kisee ka nahion janta.” From “*Sex, Scotch and Scholarship*”, “Upper Allah, Talley Jalla. Jalley dey sir tey khalla” from “*How the Sikhs Lost their Kingdom*”

With Khushwant Singh’s literary work, it is observed that he has utilized affixation, reduplication and even compounding systems of languages to create a required effect on the reader. The utilization of suffix or prefix is possible only when a writer has a minute observation of the community around and an apt understanding of the situation and appropriate usage of either prefix or suffix makes the conversation more reliable and genuine. This was one of the admirable style of Khushwant Singh who adorably inserted such terminologies seems very local and normal. Boxwallas, Gymkhana, Pro-pak, deflowered, unshaken, baw-baw, curiosity-phuriosity, oxford-phoxford are some of the peculiar formations by Khushwant Singh to add on value to his literary work. His versatility in describing every single moment of life with his alluring linguistic kept him always a stylistic originator of his own style.

Singh’s pen has the power to produce the reality of the day and the issues those prolongs in modern days. The charisma of local language to put on the emotions real on paper was an unbeatable talent of Khushwant Singh. He has his own multi fronting styles to portray the characters and make his own soul talk. His characters speak his soul. His writing always displayed the emotions, his deep thoughts and even his inner self to his readers very clearly and wisely. He was a creative English writer. Each of his novels is the evidences that he was a live writer and his writings were lively and so very famous.

The most significant aspect of Khushwant Singh's writing was the blend of local language well integrated with English language. His illustrative style of writing helped him to present his novelistic work. He was able to craft or visualize the ground level reality and could lay down artistically on the piece of paper.

He was a man who believed always in righteousness and he was in love with humanity. His pen has a dare to write anything what he felt about anybody irrespective of his gender, caste, position, designation, influence etc. His fearless writing made him not to forgive anybody who is against the humanity, human values and ethics. He used to say that whatever I think I write. And he did so. This is what the style is. It is just a reflection of one's own personality.

Apart, Khushwant Singh was a comic writer even. He used his sense of humor, wit and satire to create many scenes in many creations to indulge the reader into big laughter. He was a gentle writer who had an expertise to create pleasant and interesting stories. To name few, *Karma*, *Kusum*, *The Mark of Vishnu* is some of the conceptions of Khushwant Singh proving him to be a man with great sense of humor.

Khushwant Singh was proclaimed ironic writer for his creations like *The Company of Women*, *The Rape and Black Jasmine*, *Kusum*. These are the write ups of his credit dealing specifically with the aspects of love and sex. According to Khushwant Singh, love and sex are the two essential aspects of human life. The novel authored by Khushwant Singh, *The Company of Women* is the celebration of love, sex and passion. Here in this novel, he has produced erotic and endlessly entertaining love and sex. His style being narrative has always kept the reader intact with interest in reading and always headed the curiosity to go ahead with the piece of art.

Khushwant Singh has a wide diameter of writing which is devoted to his journalistic work. Khushwant was very clear and blunt in his writings. Whatever he thought he wrote. One should admire the freedom Khushwant Singh enjoyed with his pen. To end, Khushwant Singh could be characterized as malicious, the most ironic, lustful, humorous, witty, critical, fearless, courageous, the most frank, kind, believer of humanity and so on. His intimate knowledge of rural and urban India and his acute observation made him an impactful and the liveliest author and the novelist. He has a great faith in divine power, love and humanity which can be experience in many of his masterpieces.

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